

Wideband Inductive Coplanar Waveguide Fed Slot Antenna with Various Slot

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Abstract – This communication presents a wideband inductive CPW fed slot antenna. Initially, a simple, narrow slot antenna is designed at the center of the ground plane and fed by an inductive coplanar waveguide (CPW) line. It is a well-known fact that the narrow slot responds to narrow bandwidth in return loss characteristics. An additional slot is then introduced, along with a circular loop through two narrow slits on the main radiating slot. This modification results in the proposed design responding to 540 MHz bandwidth in return loss characteristics. Furthermore, the radiation pattern of the proposed topology is also analyzed at its resonance frequency.

Keywords – Inductive feed, coplanar wave guide (CPW), Slot antenna, wideband.

1. Introduction

Slot antennas are being considered for use in modern communication systems because of their appealing characteristics, such as their low profile, light weight, wide frequency bandwidth, ease of integration with monolithic microwave integrated circuits, low cost, and fabrication ease. In comparison to standard microstrip antennas, these antennas offer a number of advantages, including excellent impedance matching and omni-directional radiation pattern. The CPW feeding mechanism is used in the design of the slot antenna because it has a number of advantages over microstrip line feed, including low dispersion, low radiation leakage, and ease of integration with active devices. Because etching is required on both sides of the dielectric substrate, misalignment can occur when the microstrip line is used to feed the antenna. The slot is excited using the CPW feeding technique because the slot and the feeding line are etched on one side, preventing alignment errors.

Techniques for miniaturizing slot antennas are described in [1]-[4]. Brief discussions on wideband slot antennas are presented in [5]-[7], while [8]-[9] report on the wideband microstrip fed slot antenna. The inductive CPW feed DRA antenna is illustrated in [10].

This work discusses a technique for enhancing the bandwidth of an inductive CPW feed slot antenna topology through the use of an additional slot, a circular loop, and narrow slits. Compared to a normal slot antenna, the proposed antenna achieves a wide bandwidth of 540MHz. Furthermore, the E and H plane radiation characteristics are analyzed at the resonant frequency.

2. Antenna Design

The inductive CPW fed slot antenna is presented in Figure 1. The FR-4 microwave substrate is applied to construct the slot antenna with standard height 1.60 mm. The permittivity of FR-4 microwave substrate is 4.4. The antenna design parameters are listed in Table 1. Then Figure 1 is further modified using an addition slot, a circular loop and narrow slit on the main radiation slot. The top view of antenna topology is depicted in Figure 2. Throughout the paper, the design topologies are analyzed using the Ansys HFSS simulation tool [11].

Figure 1. Reference slot antenna (Top view)

Figure 2. Proposed slot antenna (Top view)

Table 1: Dimension of antenna designing parameter

Parameters	Description	Value(mm)
L	Antenna length	70
$L1$	Space between two CPW line	12
$L2$	CPW line length	34.4
$L3$	Slot length at one side	8.2
$L4$	Addition slot length	30
LSL	Slot length	30
W	Antenna width	70
$W1$	CPW line width	0.8
$W2$	Slot width	1.2
$W3$	Space between two slot	1.4
$W4$	Circular loop width	2
$W5$	Width of narrow slit	2
D	Diameter of circular loop	10

3. Results and discussions

A hemisphere dielectric resonator was introduced in the literature [9] to enhance the matching condition of the inductive coplanar waveguide feed slot antenna, which is otherwise known to have poor matching properties. It is known to all that return loss is a measure of the amount of power that is reflected back to the source when a signal is transmitted from an antenna. It is expressed in decibels (dB) and is calculated as the ratio of the power of the reflected wave to the power of the incident wave. To keep the paper concise, the deficient return loss properties of the reference antenna are not displayed.

Figure 3. Return loss characteristics of proposed inductive CPW feed slot antenna

After the introduction of an additional slot, circular loop and narrow slits, the proposed topology is resonate at 3.49 GHz frequency. The return loss plot is shown in Figure 3. It should be noted that the proposed antenna produces 540 MHz wide bandwidth with good matching characteristics. Inductive CPW feed slot antennas are known for their compact size, low profile, and ease of integration with other microwave components. They are often used in applications that require a wide bandwidth, such as in wireless communication systems, radar systems, and satellite communication systems.

The E plane is defined at $\varphi=0^\circ$, whereas H-plane is defined at $\varphi=90^\circ$ in spherical coordinate system. The E-plane radiation pattern describes the distribution of the electric field intensity as a function of angle, while the H-plane radiation pattern describes the distribution of the magnetic field intensity. At the resonance frequency of 3.49 GHz, both E-plane and H-plane radiation patterns were analyzed. It is significant to note that the cross-polarization was found to be distorted in the H-plane, while in the E-plane, the cross-polarization levels were below the acceptable threshold. The simulated radiation pattern at 3.49 GHz is depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Radiation characteristics of proposed inductive CPW feed slot antenna at 3.49 GHz

4. Conclusion

In summary, the proposed antenna is a simple and easy-to-construct solution for wideband applications. By adding an extra slot, a circular loop, and thin slits to the antenna structure, the topology achieves a 540MHz bandwidth and exhibits good E-plane radiation characteristics. The antenna is well-suited for various wireless communication systems, radar systems, and satellite communication systems.

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